

EMERGING THERAPIES IN ONCOLOGY: A REVIEW

Dr. Sachin A. Nitave*, Principal Dr. J. J. Magdum Trusts Anil Alias Pintu Magdum Memorial Pharmacy College, Dharangutti, Tal. Shirol, Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India.

Abstract:

There are several types of cancer treatments including surgery, chemotherapy, radiation therapy, hormonal therapy etc. Even after several developments in medical science, cancer is responsible for millions of deaths every year worldwide. However, the latest advances are changing the scenario. There is no particular cause of cancer. Some factors that can increase risk of developing the disease include smoking, exposure to radiation, and a family history of cancer. The best way to prevent the disease is to avoid the risk factors that can lead to its development. Cancer is a disease that can be difficult to treat. However, new advances in the treatment of cancer can help people battle and even overcome this.

Keywords: Cancer, Treatment, Disease, Emerging.

Introduction:

Cancer is a diseases that occur when cells divide uncontrollably and spread to other parts of the body. Oncology is a branch which deals with study and treatment of tumors. Cancer can start almost anywhere in the human body, which is made up of trillions of cells. Normally, human cells grow and multiply (through a process called cell division) to form new cells as the body needs them. When cells grow old or become damaged, they die, and new cells take their place.

Sometimes this orderly process breaks down, and abnormal or damaged cells grow and multiply when they shouldn't. These cells may form tumors, which are lumps of tissue. Tumors can be cancerous or not cancerous (benign).

Cancerous tumors spread into, or invade, nearby tissues and can travel to distant places in the body to form new tumors (a process called metastasis). Cancerous tumors may also be called malignant tumors. Many cancers form solid tumors, but cancers of the blood, such as leukemias, generally do not.

Benign tumors do not spread into, or invade, nearby tissues. When removed, benign tumors usually don't grow back, whereas cancerous tumors sometimes do. Benign tumors can sometimes be quite large, however. Some can cause serious symptoms or be life threatening, such as benign tumors in the brain¹.

With advancements in the field of medicine, availability of top-notch treatment options, and superior infrastructure, the chances of treating fatal diseases are high. Today emerging technologies have made it possible to save humankind from such fatal diseases. Hence, 80% of cancer treatments are successful today when identified in the initial stages. Moreover, innovative approaches to treat this disease have helped save many precious lives.

Types of Cancers²:

There are more than 100 types of cancer. Types of cancer are usually named for the organs or tissues where the cancers form. For example, lung cancer starts in the lung, and brain cancer starts in the brain. Cancers also may be described by the type of cell that formed them, such as an epithelial cell or a squamous cell.

1. **Carcinoma:** Carcinomas are the most common type of cancer. They are formed by epithelial cells, which are the cells that cover the inside and outside surfaces of the body.
2. **Sarcoma:** Sarcomas are cancers that form in bone and soft tissues, including muscle, fat, blood vessels, lymph vessels, and fibrous tissue (such as tendons and ligaments).
3. **Leukemia:** Cancers that begin in the blood-forming tissue of the bone marrow are called leukemias.
4. **Lymphoma:** Lymphoma is cancer that begins in lymphocytes (T cells or B cells). These are disease-fighting white blood cells that are part of the immune system. In lymphoma, abnormal lymphocytes build up in lymph nodes and lymph vessels, as well as in other organs of the body.
5. **Multiple Myeloma:** Multiple myeloma is cancer that begins in plasma cells, another type of immune cell.
6. **Melanoma:** Melanoma is cancer that begins in cells that become melanocytes, which are specialized cells that make melanin (the pigment that gives skin its color).

Conventional Therapies in Cancer Treatment³:

There are several types of conventional cancer treatments, including:

1. **Surgery:** The main treatment for many types of cancer, surgery removes the cancer or as much of it as possible.
2. **Chemotherapy:** Uses strong medicines to treat cancer.
3. **Radiation therapy:** Uses high energy X-rays to destroy cancer cells.
4. **Hormonal therapy:** Reduces hormone levels in the body or blocks hormones from reaching cancer cells.
5. **Targeted therapy:** As the name suggests, the therapy involves targeting the proteins of the cells and controlling their growth. Hence, the therapy is also inclusive of precision medicine. Cancer cells hide from a patient's immune system and hence can multiply speedily. This cancer treatment involves strengthening the immune system and damaging them entirely before they multiply. Hence, the therapy helps to identify the cause in its initial stages and avoid further damage.
6. **Stem cell or bone marrow treatments:** Allows high doses of anti-cancer treatment to be given or provides a new immune system to fight the cancer.
7. **Immunotherapy:** Uses medicine to help the body's immune system kill cancer cells.

Emerging Therapies in Cancer Treatment^{4,5,6,7,8,9}:

1. **CRISPR:** A blessing to mankind in the form of doctors Jennifer Doudna and Emmanuelle Charpentier turned the tables for cancer treatment. These brilliant doctors gave birth to an unimaginable and unbelievable concept of a gene-editing tool called 'Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats- CRISPR.

2. **Robotic Surgery:** The list of best and innovative approaches for cancer treatment also involves Robotic Surgery. Robotic surgery is not an alien term in today's tech-spaced medical world. Gone are the days when each surgery required huge incisions to operate on a patient. Instead, robotic surgery is a method in which the machine's robotic arms are inserted into the patient through small incisions. It involves less pain, less blood loss, and fewer scar marks. In addition, the camera attached to the robotic arms provides a 3D vision of the surgical area hence a surgeon can have a detailed look at the problematic area. Hence, robotic surgery helps to remove cancerous tissues successfully to heal a patient.
3. **Photodynamic therapy:** Uses a light-activated drug to kill cancer cells by damaging blood vessels, producing oxygen radicals, and activating the immune system.
4. **Chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) therapy:** An immunotherapy that uses recombinant receptors to redirect T lymphocytes to target cancer cells.
5. **Antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs):** A biotherapeutic that combines monoclonal antibodies with cytotoxins to deliver drugs directly to tumors.
6. **Nucleotide synthesis:** A promising antitumor treatment strategy that interferes with the active nucleotide synthesis of cancer cells.
7. **Minimally invasive surgery:** A safe and feasible option for a variety of cancers that can be performed through smaller incisions than traditional open surgery.
8. **Genomic and Personalized Medicine:** Advances in genomic profiling allow for more personalized treatment plans.

This involves:

- **Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS):** To identify genetic mutations driving the cancer, enabling tailored treatments.
 - **Liquid Biopsies:** Non-invasive tests that detect cancer-related genetic material from blood samples, offering a way to monitor treatment response and disease progression.
9. **Epigenetic Therapy:** These therapies aim to modify the epigenetic changes in cancer cells, which can affect gene expression without altering the DNA sequence. Examples include drugs targeting DNA methylation and histone modification.
 10. **Oncolytic Virus Therapy:** This approach uses genetically modified viruses that selectively infect and kill cancer cells while sparing normal cells. Examples include Talimogene laherparepvec (T-VEC), which is used for melanoma.
 11. **Combination Therapies:** Combining different types of therapies, such as immunotherapy with targeted therapy or chemotherapy, to enhance effectiveness and overcome resistance.
 12. **Biologics and Antibody-Drug Conjugates (ADCs):** These are drugs that combine antibodies with cytotoxic agents to deliver targeted treatment directly to cancer cells. Examples include brentuximab vedotin for Hodgkin lymphoma.
 13. **Cryoablation:** Cryoablation is one of the ablation techniques which ablates the extensive tissue by freezing to lethal temperatures followed by liquid formation, causing extensive tissue. Benign and malignant primary tumors are mostly treated by this therapy.
 14. **RFA therapy:** RFA is a minimally invasive procedure and an image-guided technique using hyperthermic (high-frequency electrical currents) conditions to destroy cancer cells. Imaging techniques, such as ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), guide needle electrodes into a tumor cell. Generally, RFA is the

most effective approach for treating small-size tumors of less than 3 cm in diameter. RFA can be used in combination with other conventional cancer treatment options.

15. **Photodynamic Therapy:** This cancer treatment involves the absorption of photosensitizers by cells. The therapy exposes the cancer cells to photons. The therapy uses a drug activated by light, producing oxygen radicals in the cells and killing cancer from the root. The therapy helps treat specific parts of the body damaged due to cancer. The therapy helps to damage the blood vessels in the tumours. It ceases the blood flow in the vessels, which helps cells grow. The therapy also activates the immune system to fight back the tumour cells.
16. **Gene Therapy:** Gene therapy is the insertion of a normal copy of a defective gene in the genome to cure a specific disorder. The first application dates back to 1990 when a retroviral vector was exploited to deliver the adenosine deaminase (ADA) gene to T cells in patients with severe combined immunodeficiency (SCID). Approximately, about 2900 gene therapy clinical trials are currently ongoing, two-third of which are related to cancer. Strategies, such as expression of proapoptotic and chemosensitizing genes, expression of wild-type tumor suppressor genes, expression of genes able to solicit specific anti-tumor immune responses, and targeted silencing of oncogenes, are under evaluation for cancer gene therapy.

Conclusion:

Current methods in oncology focus on the development of safe and efficient cancer nanomedicines. Targeted medical care helped rising the biodistribution of recent or already tested chemotherapeutical agents around the specific tissue to be treated; different methods, such as sequence medical care, inhibitor molecules, supply new potentialities to cancer patients. Gene therapy acts by direct in situ insertion of exogenous genes into benign tumors. Noticeably, stem cells can be used as regenerative medicine, therapeutic carriers, drug targeting, and generation of immune cells because of having unique biological actions on other cells. On the opposite hand, thermal ablation and magnetic hyperthermia are promising alternatives to the growth surgical process. Finally, radionics and pathomics approaches facilitate the management of huge knowledge sets from cancer patients to enhance prognosis and outcomes. Much progress has been made, but many others are likely to come soon, producing more and more ad hoc personalized therapies. Further development and refinement of drug delivery systems are essential for improving therapeutic outcomes. These emerging therapies are continually being refined and tested through clinical trials, and they hold promise for more effective and personalized cancer treatment options in the future.

Acknowledgments: The author thanks the SwaLife Biotech and SwaLife Foundation for giving a platform to exchange the pharmacist's knowledge, professional growth on occasion of international pharmacy and pharmacovigilance week.

References:

1. Guide to Know About Latest Advances in Cancer Treatment, RGCIRC Team

Cancer, 20 January 2023.

2. National Cancer Institute.
3. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
4. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
5. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
6. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
7. <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
8. Innovative Approaches to Cancer Treatment: Emerging Therapies and Technologies, Narayana Health Blog.
9. New approaches and procedures for cancer treatment: Current perspectives
Dejene Tolossa Debela, SAGE Open Med. 2021; 9: 20503121211034366